

Simulation of Steelmaking Processes: An Assessment of Reduced and Full Scale Water Modelling, Numerical Simulation *vis a vis* Plant Scale Measurements

Dipak Mazumdar, Krshnavtar, Rishikesh Mishra and Prince Kumar Singh
Department Of Materials Science and Engineering
India Institute of Technology, Kanpur, 208016, India
Contacts: phone (+91-5122597328);e-mail (dipak@iitk.ac.in)

Keywords: Physical modelling; scale factor; scalability; mathematical modelling; industrial scale measurements.

INTRODUCTION

Wide spread physical and mathematical modelling of steelmaking started in the sixties and a large number of investigations on steelmaking process analysis and design, have been reported during the past half a century. In these, considerable emphasis has been laid particularly on the modelling of BOF, ladle metallurgy, tundish metallurgy, continuous casting operations. A great deal of information on the subject is already summarized through many reviews¹⁻⁶, published during the last two decades or so. These collectively demonstrate that physical and mathematical modelling is sufficiently empowering and provide steelmakers decisive advantages on such fronts as reactor design, process control, clean steel production and so on. Physical modelling of steelmaking, as the large number of investigations indicate, have been carried out with two well defined objectives i.e.,

- (i) To physically visualize phenomena such as flow, two liquid (slag-metal) mixing, vortex formation during draining etc. and to draw therefrom, useful inferences on the process dynamics and
- (ii) To carry out quantitative measurements on flow, turbulence, mixing time, solid-liquid and liquid- liquid mass transfer rates such that appropriate process models can be developed and validated.

With reference to (i), it is to be noted that water models, as employed, represent steelmaking systems approximately since many features of high temperature, chemically reacting steelmaking systems, particularly those associated with converters, furnaces and LRF (ladle refining furnaces) cannot be replicated in water models. Indeed, this has been explicitly acknowledged in the literature⁷. Yet, many water model studies on BOF, AOD converters, copper converters etc. which are essentially reacting, multiphase, non isothermal systems, have been reported in the literature. Most importantly however, water modelling results are extrapolated disregarding entirely the chemically reacting nature of such systems, known to induce many process complexities such as, phase volume changes, gas generation, temperature rise and so on⁸⁻¹². Even for water modelling of non-reacting flows such as those encountered in ladle, tundish and mold, some apprehensions seem to exist due to large differences in thermo physical properties of constituting phases (i.e., slag and metal) and limitations of operating temperature. Not many evidence that water modelling results are largely representative of the actual, exist in literature. This is of concern since smaller size water models are frequently and it is well known that flow regimes in reduced scale models tend to change significantly as geometrical scale factor goes down. It is therefore not surprising that many industrial R&D houses, in refractory and steelmaking, prefer full scale water models over their smaller counterpart to ensure realistic outcome from physical model studies. Looked at from such a stand point, validation of a mathematical model against measurements derived from small size water models, for developing a sufficiently predictive frame work warrants a closer look. It is interesting to note that despite widespread usage of small size water models to simulate ladle-tundish and mold flows as well as validation of mathematical model predictions against data derived from reduced scale models, size of models or the scale factor, and scalability of results have not been given sufficient attention in the literature.

Consequently, the purpose of the present study is to primarily examine the role of scale factor in physical and mathematical model studies steelmaking from both experimental and computational stand points. Discussion is presented with reference to physical modelling of primarily non- reacting, isothermal flows in ladle and tundish metallurgy operations. As our starting point, previous work on reduced scale physical modelling has been reviewed and analyzed critically. Following such, new experimental results from full scale as well as reduced scale water models of ladle shroud systems are presented to address the issue of scalability of two phase gas-liquid flow systems. The issue has been parallelly examined on the basis of some computational results of flow and RTD for steelmaking tundish systems at various geometrical scale factors. To demonstrate the present work, the adequacy and appropriateness of results derived from a reduced scale model study ($\lambda=0.5$) is directly evaluated against measurements of grade intermixing time in an industrial slab casting set-up. These together with relevant details are presented in the following sections.

PREVIOUS WORK

Physical Modelling of Multiphase Steel Processing Operations

In physical model investigations, gravity force driven steelmaking systems have been typically considered to be Froude dominated since steel processing units are large and that kinematic viscosity of liquid steel is small. Thus for argon-steel and corresponding air-water analogue (i.e., a two phase system), it is well known that if corresponding flow rates (of liquid or gas) is scaled in accordance to $\lambda^{2.5}$, Froude and Weber similarities can be exactly satisfied at $\lambda \sim 0.6$. On the other hand, Reynolds number similarity between model and prototype is exactly satisfied only in full scale models since steel at 1873K and water at 298K have practically similar kinematic viscosity. In multi-phase, chemically reacting flow systems involving molten steel-slag and gas, the issue is however not as straight forward as pointed above as additional complexities arise due to chemical reaction, heat generation etc. Yet, attempts have been and are being made to scale-up water modelling results for reacting flow systems and draw therefrom inferences on industrial scale operation.

Figure 1 The effect of agitation energy on mixing behavior in an 80 T converter.

Thus in 1984, while Oymo and Guthrie¹³ investigated the characteristics of combination blowing steelmaking process through water modelling, as recent as in 2015, similar attempts were made by Cao and coworkers¹⁰ to suggest operating gas flow regimes in BOF under various stirring conditions viz., top, bottom and combination blowing. These and similar other studies reported in the literature fail to recognize that injected gas in BOF and other primary refining units is in general reactive in nature (much different from argon injection into steel melt) and leads to change in phasic volumes along with temperature. Consequently, aqueous models are largely inadequate to represent such systems even as a first approximation. Given such, extrapolation of water model results to prototype steelmaking converters or furnaces, such as the one shown in Fig.1¹⁰ is uncertain and questionable. Towards this, it is instructive to note that mathematical modelling of steelmaking is sufficiently matured to address reactive gas injection into high temperature melts and associated issues. In contrast to the above, argon rinsing in ladles, transfer of liquids between ladle and tundish, fluid flow and residence time distribution in tundish etc. are reasonably accurately modeled through water model systems since inter-phase heat and mass transfer and chemical reactions, post vacuum degassing (VD) operations are minimal. It is to the modelling of such non-reacting (and practically isothermal) flows and associated transport phenomena (as in in ladle, shroud and tundish etc.), the present work has been primarily concerned with.

In the modelling of isothermal and chemically non-reacting flows in steelmaking, the geometrical scale factor, particularly if too small, can become an issue of concern. Heat size and reactor capacity in steel industries are in general massive (mini mills and integrated steel plants employ reactors having capacity typically in the range of 50-300 T, rendering a minimal total reactor volume of 10 m³ or so), while in water modelling, diversely different and reduced size models have been deployed; full scale water models have been rarely seen though, not entirely uncommon. To elucidate the point further, vessel size deployed in some widely reported physical model studies of flow and mixing phenomena in ladles¹⁴⁻¹⁸ are shown in Table I, in which, corresponding geometrical scale factors, referenced to small and modest size ladles in the industry, are also summarized. There, a wide range of scale factor (in the range of 0.04-0.50) in different studies, is readily apparent. It is therefore naturally important to investigate if observations derived from water models, irrespective of their size, are representative of the actual, even if phenomena such as chemical reaction and heat transfer are of secondary importance. In the subsequent section, an attempt has been made to address this critical concern with some new experimental data, computational results and industrial scale measurements.

Table I Model sizes in some widely reported physical model investigations and the corresponding range geometrical scale factors with reference to 50 T and 185 T steelmaking ladles.

Sequence number	Investigators	Subject	Vessel diameter (D), m	Estimated geometrical scale factor, λ with reference to:	
				60 T ladle (D=2.2m)	150 T ladle (D=3.65m)
1	Mazumdar and Guthrie (1986)	Ladle flow and mixing	1.12	0.50	0.30
2	Stapurewicz and Themelis (1987)	Ladle mixing	0.66	0.28	0.17
3	Meitz and Oeters (1988)	Ladle mixing	0.63	0.30	0.18
4	Mazumdar, Nakajima and Guthrie (1988)	Multiphase flow	0.30	0.135	0.082
5	Iguchi, Nakamura and Tsujino (1998)	Ladle flow and mixing	0.20 and 0.14	0.09;0.06	0.05;0.04

Figure 2 Extent of mismatch between model and prototype (a) Reynolds number and (b) Weber number in Froude dominated gas – liquid two phase flows as a function of geometrical scale factors and the desirable range of scale factor for best possible outcome.

In isothermal, non-reacting flow simulation, dynamic similarity between model and prototype is dictated by the momentum conservation equation, expressed in dimensionless form as:

$$F(N_{Re}, N_{Fr}, N_{We}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

The above implies equality of Reynolds, Froude and Weber numbers between model and prototype. However, in reduced scale model studies with water as the bulk liquid, seldom simultaneous equality of all three numbers is possible. If Froude dominated flows are assumed to prevail in large steel processing units (except perhaps the near wall regions, this is largely expected to hold good) (this further implies, $u_{mod} = \lambda^{0.5} u_{fs}$), it is readily shown that Webber and Reynolds number similitude, between two phase, gas-liquid prototype steelmaking system and corresponding water models, can be expressed in terms of the geometrical scale factor as:

$$N_{We,mod} = 3.13 \times \lambda^2 N_{We,prot.} \quad (2)$$

$$N_{Re,mod} = \lambda^{3/2} N_{Re,prot.} \quad (3)$$

The above relationships implicitly implies that even in idealized process simulation (no chemical and thermal interactions, little or no slag etc.), Reynolds and Weber number tends to assume significantly more importance as model scale factor goes down. Given such,

physical conditions in a very small size model are likely to be considerably different from those prevalent in their industrial counterpart. Indeed, as shown in Fig.2, the difference between model and prototype Reynolds and Weber numbers changes drastically as the geometrical scale factor decreases. In other words, with reduction in scale factor, viscous and surface tension forces or Reynolds and Weber numbers get unduly amplified (relative to inertial and gravitation forces or Froude number) leading to a significantly different flow regimes particularly in small size water models. As a consequence of such, results derived from very small scale water models are unlikely likely to be representative of the actual. It appears from Fig.2 that best comprise is ensured provided the chosen scale factor lies in the range 0.5~0.7. However this needs to be substantiated with further analysis and experimental measurements.

Beyond scale factor or the size of the physical models, representation of actual steel processing units via different types of liquids (as in the case of steel-argon slag system) poses serious limitation as far as scaling up of result is concerned. To illustrate this point further, different correlations on mixing time, deduced from water model investigations are examined in the following. Thus, more than three decades ago, based on their observations from a relatively large water model ladle (D=1.12m), Mazumdar and Guthrie¹⁴ proposed the following correlation for mixing time (in SI Unit) in a slag-less ,inert gas stirred steelmaking ladle systems:

$$\tau_{\text{mix},95\%} = 25.4Q^{-0.33}L^{-1.0}R^{2.33} \quad (4)$$

in which, L is the depth of liquid, R is the radius of the vessel (=0.5D) and Q is the gas flow rate corrected to 1873K and hydrostatic pressure at the mid- bath depth level. Many subsequent physical model investigations have indicated that physical characteristics of the upper phase liquid influence mixing times. Consequently, modified form of Eq.(4), was also developed for equivalent slag covered system¹⁹ , viz.,

$$\tau_{\text{mix},95\%} \approx 152Q^{-0.33}L^{-1.0}R^{2.33}\eta^{0.3}v_s^{0.033}\left(\frac{\Delta\rho}{\rho_L}\right)^{-0.044} \quad (5)$$

In Eq.(5) v_s is the kinematic viscosity of the upper phase liquid, ρ_L is the bulk phase density and $\Delta\rho$ is the differential density between the bulk and upper phase liquid. In contrast to the above, significantly different mixing correlation, deduced from small size water model ladles (D=0.14m and 0.20m) and containing liquids of higher kinematic viscosity was however proposed by Iguchi and coworkers¹⁸. Their correlation expectedly shows the dependence of Reynolds number (Re) and hence bulk fluid properties on mixing time, as shown below:

$$\tau_{\text{mix}}\left(\frac{L}{D}\right)\left(\frac{g}{D}\right)^{0.5} = 4.21 \times 10^3 \text{Re}^{-0.47} \quad (6)$$

The brief discussion presented above clearly indicates that inferences drawn from water model studies tend to depend on scale factor as well as on fluids used to represent multi-phase, steelmaking systems. In other words, at all scale factors and with any type of fluids, results obtained from physical model studies may not be entirely corroborate the actual and therefore, necessarily not scalable. What is discussed above in the context of ladle mixing is also largely true of water model investigation of shroud, tundish and SEN (submerged entry nozzle) as the latter are approximated reasonably well as non- reacting flow systems. To analyses the issue further and explore a practical and universal geometrical scale factor, physical modelling and computational results supported by some industrial scale measurements are presented in the following section.

PRESENT WORK

The Role of Scale Factor in Modelling: Experimental Assessment

Physical and mathematical modelling of two phase, gas-liquid flows in full scale, water model ladle shroud systems have been reported recently by Singh and Mazumdar²⁰⁻²². As seen from Fig.3, co-injection of a non-reactive gas into a ladle shroud typically produces a free jet liquid followed by an intensely mixed gas-liquid flow region. In the range of operating parameters of interest, it was demonstrated that the dimensionless free jet length can be related to physical dimension of the ladle shroud, thermo-physical properties of fluids and operating flow rates via the following relationship(in SI unit):

$$\left(\frac{L_{\text{Jet}}}{D_{\text{CN}}}\right) = 2.8 \times 10^{-2} \left(\frac{Q_{\text{G}}}{Q_{\text{L}}}\right)^{1.14} \left(\frac{g D_{\text{CN}}^5}{Q_{\text{L}}^2}\right)^{0.8} \left(\frac{\sigma D_{\text{CN}}^3}{\rho_{\text{L}} Q_{\text{L}}^2}\right)^{-0.9} \left(\frac{\rho_{\text{G}}}{\rho_{\text{L}}}\right)^{-0.3} \left(\frac{D_{\text{sh}}}{D_{\text{CN}}}\right)^{2.0} \quad (7)$$

In Eq.(7), L_{jet} is the free liquid jet length (m), Q_{G} is the gas flow rate (m^3/s), Q_{L} is the liquid flow rate (m^3/s), D_{sh} is shroud diameter (m), D_{CN} is the collector nozzle diameter (m), σ is the interfacial tension (N/m) and ρ_{G} as well as ρ_{L} are respectively density of gas and liquid (kg/m^3).

Figure 3 Full scale water model of a slab casting ladle shroud illustrating the formation of free liquid jet and an intensely mixed gas-liquid region at typical flow rates.

Table II Physical dimensions and operating condition in industrial and model slab casting shroud systems

Parameters	Industrial slab casting shroud	Full scale model slab casting shroud	0.66 scale water model shroud
Length (mm)	1690	1690	1120
Internal shroud diameter (mm)	110±10	95	62.8
Collector Nozzle diameter(mm)	70	60	40
Gas injection port diameter (mm)	6.35	6.35	6.35
Liquid	Steel	Water	Water
Mass flow rate of liquid (kg/s)	42 - 55	3.32 – 5.65	1.16 – 2.0
Volumetric flow rate of liquid (m^3/s)	$58.3 \times 10^{-4} - 76.4 \times 10^{-4}$	$33.3 \times 10^{-4} - 56.6 \times 10^{-4}$	$11.66 \times 10^{-4} - 20.0 \times 10^{-4}$
Gas	Argon	Air	Air
Volumetric flow rate of gas (m^3/s) (Industrial values are referenced to 1873K and 1 atm. pressure)	$13.0 \times 10^{-4} - 16.0 \times 10^{-4}$	$1.66 \times 10^{-4} - 14.16 \times 10^{-4}$	$0.29 \times 10^{-4} - 9 \times 10^{-4}$
Volumetric flow rate ratio ($Q_{\text{gas}}/ Q_{\text{liq}}$)	0.17 – 0.22	0.05 – 0.25	0.05-0.45
Shroud immersion depth [measured from tundish free surface (mm)]	100-400	100	100

To directly assess the issue of scalability and the role of scale factors in two phase non-reactive, gas-liquid flow systems, two different, geometrically similar, PERSPEX™ ladle shrouds, having scale factors 1 and 0.66 (e.g., Table II) were applied. It is to be noted here that Weber similarity between a full scale steel processing unit and corresponding water model is ensured provided $\lambda \sim 0.6$ or so. This is however not true in the present situation since same fluids are employed both in the model and the full scale shroud systems. Physical dimensions and operating flow rates in the two shroud systems are summarized in Table II. Since flow in a shroud can be taken to be inertial and gravity force dominated consequently, corresponding liquid flow rates, shown in Table II, necessary to maintain dynamic similarity between two geometrically similar shroud systems, I and II, can be deduced from:

$$Q_{L,I,0.66} = \lambda^{2.5} Q_{L,II,1.0} \quad (8)$$

For identical gas to liquid loading ratio, corresponding ratios of dimensionless free liquid jet lengths in the two shroud systems I and II, can be correlated, on the basis of Eq.(7) via the geometrical scale factor λ , as:

$$\left[\left(\frac{\left(\frac{L_{\text{Jet}}}{D_{\text{CN}}} \right)_I}{\left(\frac{L_{\text{Jet}}}{D_{\text{CN}}} \right)_{II}} \right) \right] = \left[\left(\frac{D_{\text{CN},I}}{D_{\text{CN},II}} \right)^3 \left(\frac{Q_{L,II,1.0}}{Q_{L,I,0.66}} \right)^2 \right]^{-0.9} = \lambda^{1.8} \quad (9)$$

Since, $D_{\text{CN},I} / D_{\text{CN},II} = \lambda = 0.66$, consequently, relationship between dimensionless liquid free jet lengths in the two geometrically and dynamically similar shroud systems, operated with similar fluids can be expressed as:

$$\left[\left(\frac{\left(\frac{L_{\text{Jet}}}{D_{\text{CN}}} \right)_I}{\left(\frac{L_{\text{Jet}}}{D_{\text{CN}}} \right)_{II}} \right) \right] = 0.47 \quad (10)$$

or, in terms of the corresponding absolute liquid free jet lengths, as:

$$\frac{L_{\text{Jet},I,0.66}}{L_{\text{Jet},II,1.0}} = \lambda^{2.8} \quad (11)$$

The adequacy of Eq.(10) has been assessed directly against measured liquid free jet lengths in the two water model shroud systems i.e., the full scale and the 0.66 scale shrouds respectively, at various corresponding liquid and gas flow rates. The comparison is illustrated in Fig.4(a). There, near perfect agreement between corresponding free liquid jet lengths is readily evident demonstrating essentially that experimental results of two phase flows derived from a reasonably size water model ladle shroud are reasonably scalable. In contrast, when experiments were carried out in a significantly smaller size, geometrically similar model shroud ($\lambda=0.42$) at appropriately gas and liquid flow rates, predicted and experimental dimensionless jet lengths were found to be far different from those predicted by Eq.(9). This is illustrated in Fig.4(b). There, experimental dimensionless jet length values in the smaller size model are

seen to be consistently higher than the corresponding scaled down estimates, illustrating a systemic trend of deviation, a consequence of the inadequacy of scaling laws.

Figure 4 (a) Scalability of experimental results between two water model ladle shroud systems ($\lambda=1.0$ and $\lambda=0.66$) demonstrating the adequacy of a reasonably size water model and (b) failure of scaling laws at $\lambda=0.42$

Table III Model tundish and operating parameters at different scales *vis a vis* those in the prototype steelmaking tundish.

Parameters	0.5 scale water model	0.66 scale water model	The bloom casting tundish (Prototype)
Operating parameters			
Mass flow rate (kg/s)	0.336	0.661	13.5
Tundish frontal length at base(mm)	1600	2112	3200
Maximum tundish width at base (mm)	790	1043	1580
Melt depth (mm)	350	462	700
Inlet diameter (mm)	25	33	50
Outlet diameter (mm)	7	19	30
Volumetric air/argon injection rate, m ³ /s	0.235x10 ⁻⁴ - 0.30x10 ⁻⁴	0.470x10 ⁻⁴ - 0.60x10 ⁻⁴	1.33x10 ⁻⁴ - 1.7x10 ⁻⁴
Values considered in physical and mathematical simulations			
Working fluid	water	water	steel
Density(kg/m ³)	998	998	7200
Liquid dynamic viscosity (mPa)	0.001003	0.001003	0.0077
Temperature (K)	298	298	1840-1870
Gas density,(kg/m ³)			0.259(at 298K)-1.62 (at 2573 K)
Gas dynamic viscosity			2.12x10 ⁻⁵
Interfacial tension, N/m	0.072	0.072	1.6
Tracer amount (kg)	0.15	0.15	7.5

The Role of Scale Factor in Modelling: Computational Assessment

To assess the role of scale factor in modelling further from an alternative, computational stand point, and to numerically verify the trend of observations presented in Fig.4, numerical simulation of steady state flow and residence time distributions (RTD) in a 3-strand bloom casting tundish system was carried for different bloom casting tundish dimensions having geometrical scale factor in the range 0.5 and 1.0. As our first step, a slag-less tundish system was considered in which, co-injection of argon/air in the shroud was assumed. This allowed us to adopt a two-phase flow calculation procedure to simulate flow and associated RTD phenomena in the tundish. Physical dimensions of the prototype and the scaled models are summarized in Table III, in which through-put rates have been scaled on the basis of Froude modelling criterion. Details of the steady state, two phase, turbulent flow model are summarized in ref. 23 and consequently, not reproduced here.

In Fig.5, numerically predicted “C” Curves for different scale factors and the prototype are shown. There, it is at once evident that full scale water model simulations are practically identical to that of the prototype. This essentially indicates negligible influence of thermo-physical properties of gas and bulk liquid on the resultant two phase flows and RTD phenomena in tundish systems.

Nevertheless, computed RTD curves in relatively smaller models are seen to differ from that of the prototype with diminishing geometrical scale factor illustrating a trend, consistent with findings reported in the immediately preceding section. In steelmaking tundish systems, flow intensity is known to be sluggish and therefore, as such, relative importance of viscous and surface tension forces are expected to be somewhat more pronounced. Thus, RTD curves, even from reasonably size tundish water models, are seen to deviate somewhat from that of the full scale or prototype. Differences in RTD expectedly translate to differences in the estimated mean residence time and flow volume fractions as seen from Table IV. Given the trends of experimental and computational results presented so far, substantial difference between prototype behavior and those deduced from models are likely, particularly if scale factors are small and as low as 0.1 or 0.2. Equivalent three phase computations are being currently carried out to test the present hypothesis in the context of modelling of slag covered, steelmaking tundish system.

Figure 5 Numerically computed Residence Time Distribution (RTD) curves in the prototype as well as in water models for different geometrical scale factors.

Table IV Estimated RTD parameters and flow volumes in the prototype and in water models at different geometrical scale factors.

Tundish system	Scale	Nominal residence time, s	Estimated residence time distribution parameters from C curves			
			Average dimensionless residence time, Θ_{av}	Plug flow volume fraction, V_{plug}	Dead flow volume fraction, V_{dead}	Mixed flow volume fraction, V_{mix}
Steel	Prototype	1161	0.8	0.245	0.2	0.55
Water	1	1161	0.8	0.23	0.2	0.57
Water	0.66	1077	0.74	0.166	0.26	0.57
Water	0.5	806	0.82	0.183	0.18	0.64

The Role of Scale Factor in Modelling: Industrial Scale Measurements and Validation

To investigate the issue of scalability of water modelling results directly against industrial scale measurements, grade intermixing studies in a 0.5 scale water model of a slab casting systems were carried out. Parallel to such, two set of industrial scale trials were conducted in a 32 T, single strand, slab casting tundish to measure intermixing time during sequence casting of different grades of steel (i.e., with and without boron as well as low and high manganese steels). Industrial casting conditions are summarised in Table V. While electrical conductivity measurement technique was applied in the laboratory to measure 85% grade intermixing time in a half scale, geometrically and dynamically similar water model tundish, intermixed slab weights were directly estimated on the shop floor based on chemical analysis of actual slab produced. Experimentally measured intermixing time from the geometrically and dynamically similar water model system was scaled up as per scaling laws (i.e., corresponding time scales in geometrically and dynamically similar systems vary in proportion to $\lambda^{0.5}$) and translated to equivalent slab weight embodying casting speed, mold dimensions and density of steel. Scaled up weight of transition slab weight and corresponding industrial scale values are presented in Table VI. There, it is at once evident that results derived from a half scale geometrically and dynamically similar water model tundish corroborate reasonably well with the corresponding industrial practices.

Table V Industrial casting conditions during sequence casting of two different set of steel slabs having different chemical composition.

Parameters	Trial 1	Trial 2
Casting Speed (meters/minutes)	3.6	3
Casting Slab Width (mm)	1450	1500
Casting Slab Thickness (mm)	55	63
Total throughput rate from tundish to mould (m ³ /s)	0.287	0.254
85 % Mixing time	587.33	494
85 % Mixing Length	35.24	24.70
Density of steel (kg/m ³)	7600	7600
Mixed Slab Weight (Tons)	21.36	17.74

Table VI Scaled up and actual transition slab weight during continuous casting from a 32 T slab casting tundish (Actual residual liquid in tundish=10 tonne).

Trial	Transition slab weight, tonnes		(Mixing Weight Trial – Mixing Weight Simulation)
	Scaled up amount	Actual amount	Mixing Weight Simulation * 100
1	19.48	21.36	+9.65 %
2	19.48	17.74	-9.80 %

As a final point, physical and mathematical model results in conjunction with plant scale trials have clearly indicated that *bulk phase* flow phenomena are captured reasonably well in water models provided geometrical scale factor is sufficiently large and chemical and thermal effects are insignificant. Such observations, it is cautioned, should not be generalized but rather, examined carefully on a case to case basis, to address the issue of scalability of results. For example, in water model investigation of mass transfer between upper phase and bulk liquid, physical properties of the upper phase liquid is likely to be of considerable importance since these tend to influence droplet shape and size and their sub-surface trajectories determining surface area, retention time and hence the rate of two-fluid mass transfer. In contrast to such, RTD in steelmaking tundish system is unlikely to be dependent on the upper phase characteristics to a large extent. The present study as a corollary suggests that as large a water model as possible should be deployed to generate mathematical model validation data set. This is important to configure a physically realistic and sufficiently predictive mathematical model suitable for industrial scale process analysis.

CONCLUSIONS

Diverse size of water models have been deployed in physical model studies of various steel processing units. As far as realistic simulation of high temperature steelmaking systems is concerned, it has been argued that water modelling is largely inadequate to simulate chemically reacting and thermally inhomogeneous flows in BOF, AOD, and LRF etc. In contrast, water models of reasonable size should suffice and produce results which are sufficiently scalable as far as modelling of flow related transport processes in ladle, tundish, shroud, SEN etc. are concerned. For these latter of processing units, it is shown that scale of the model rather than the physical characteristics of the upper phase liquid, is more important and is expected to exert considerable influence on model outcome. In the absence of plant scale data, it is advocated that in the pursuit of developing sufficiently realistic process models, adequacy of model predictions should preferably be assessed against experimental observations derived from reasonably size water models.

REFERENCES

1. D.Sichen, "Modelling Related to Secondary Metallurgy", *Steel Research International*, Vol.83(9), 2012, pp.825-843.
2. D.Mazumdar and R.Guthrie, "Physical and Mathematical Modelling of Gas Stirred Ladle Systems", *ISIJ International*, Vol. (1), 1995, pp.1-20.
3. B.G Thomas, "Modeling of the Continuous Casting of Steel—Past, Present, and Future", *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions B*, Vol. 33(6), 2002, pp. 795-812.

4. L.Zhang and S.Taniguchi, "Fundamentals of Inclusion Removal from Steel by Bubble Floatation", *International Materials Review*, Vol.45(2), 2000, pp.59-82.
5. Liu et.al, "A Review Of Physical And Numerical Approaches For The Study Of Gas Stirring In Ladle Metallurgy", *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions*, Vol.50B, February 2019, pp. 555-577.
6. D.Mazumdar, "Review, Analysis Of Modelling of Continuous Casting Tundish Systems", *Steel Research International*, 2018, 1800279.
7. D.Mazumdar and J.W.Evans: "Elements of Physical Modelling", *Modelling of Steelmaking Processes*, CRC Press, Boca Raton, USA, 2009, pp.99-138.
8. Z.Lai, Z.Xie and L. Zhong: "Influence of Bottom Tuyere Configuration on Bath Stirring in a Top and Bottom Combined Blown Converter", *ISIJ International*, Vol.48(6), 2008, pp.793-798.
9. Q.Li, M.Li, Z. ZOU, "Penetration of Supersonic Jets Impinging on Bath Surface in BOF Steelmaking", *Procd., 6th Int. Cong. On Science and Technology of Steelmaking*, Beijing, China, Vol.1, 2015, pp.187-190.
10. L.Cao, Z.Wang, Q.Liu, X.Lu and F.Xie, "Physical Modeling Research on The Stirring Characteristics And Mixing Effect of An 80-T Converter", *Procd., 6th International Congress on the Science and Technology of Steelmaking*, Beijing, China, 2015,pp.171-174.
11. S.Sabah and G. Brooks, "Splashing in Oxygen Steelmaking", *ISIJ International*, Vol.54(4), 2014, pp. 836-844.
12. L.Cao, Y.Wang, Q.Liu and X.Feng, "Physical and Mathematical Modelling of Multiphase Flows In A Converter", *ISIJ International*, Vol.58(2), 2018, pp.1-12.
13. D.Oymo and R.Guthrie, "Mixed Gas Blowing", *Procd. 4th PTD Conference*, Iron and Steel Society, Warrendale, 1984, p.45-53.
14. D.Mazumdar and R.Guthrie, "Mixing Models For Gas Stirred Ladle Systems", *Metall. Trans.*, Vol.17B, 1986, pp.725-733.
15. D.Mazumdar, H.Nakajima and R.Guthrie, "Possible Roles of Upper Slag Phases On The Fluid Dynamics of Gas Stirred Ladles", *Metall.Trans.*, Vol.19B, 1988, pp.705-708.
16. J.Meitz and F.Oeters, "Model Experiments on Mixing Phenomena In Gas-Stirred Melts", *Steel Research International*, Vol.59(2), 1988, p.52-59.
17. T.Stapurewicz and N.J.Themelis, " Mixing And Mass Transfer Phenomena In Bottom-Injected Gas-Liquid Reactors", *Canadian Metallurgical Quarterly*,Vol.26(2), 1987, p.123-128.
18. M.Iguchi, K.Nakamura, and R.Tsujino, "Mixing Time And Fluid Flow Phenomena In Liquids of Varying Kinematic Viscosities Agitated By Bottom Gas Injection" *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions*, Vol.29B, 1998, pp.569-575.
19. S.P.Patil, D.Satish, M.Peranadanathan and D.Mazumdar, "Mixing Models For Slag Covered Ladles" *ISIJ International*, Vol.50(8), 2010, pp.1117-1124.
20. Dipak Mazumdar, Prince K Singh and Rohit Tiwari, "Shrouded Transfer of Molten Steel From Ladle To Tundish: Current Understanding, Mathematical Modelling And New Insight", *ISIJ International*, Vol. 58(8), August 2018, pp. 1545–1547.
21. P.K. Singh and Dipak Mazumdar, "A Physical Model Study of Two-Phase Gas-Liquid Flows In A Ladle Shroud", *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions B*, Vol. 49, August 2018, pp. 1945-1962.
22. P.K. Singh and D.Mazumdar, "Mathematical Modelling of Gas-Liquid, Two-Phase Flows In A Ladle Shroud", *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions B*, Vol. 50 (2), April 2019, pp. 1091-1103.
23. D. Mazumdar and Rishikesh Mishra, "Improvement of Steel Cleanliness In Tundish Operations: Physical Modelling, Numerical Simulation And Industrial Scale Validation", *Procd. Clean Steel10 (CD-ROM version)*, Budapest, Hungary, 2018.